

COMPLEX CHROMI-SELENATES.

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Formation of the complexes, chromi-selenic acid, chromi-seleni-chromic acid and romium chromi-seleni-chromate has been studied.

Recoura (*Compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 577; 1893, 116, 1367; 1893, 117, 37, 131) found that green chromium sulphate combined with aqueous solutions of sulphuric acid and alkaline sulphates in different molecular proportions to form compounds, from which the sulphate ion was not precipitated by barium salts, although the metal introduced with the sulphate could be recognised by means of the usual tests. So these compounds were regarded as salts of a complex acid, chromo-sulphuric acid, $H_2[Cr_2(SO_4)_4]$, resembling hydro-chromi-cyanic acid, $H_2[Cr(CN)_6]$ and chromi-oxalic acid, $H_2[Cr(C_2O_4)_2]$. These chromi-sulphates are not very stable as the sulphate ion in the aqueous solutions is gradually precipitated even in the cold and at once on heating. The chromi-sulphuric acid is stable in the dry air but unstable in aqueous solutions, gradually changing into violet chromium sulphate.

Chromi-di- or tri-sulphuric acids have been obtained by using 2 or 3 molecular proportions of sulphuric acid. They are green powders stable in the solid condition but gradually decompose in solutions. Their constitutions are most probably $H_2[Cr_2(SO_4)_4]$, $H_4[Cr_2(SO_4)_6]$, $H_6[Cr_2(SO_4)_8]$. The corresponding alkaline salts have also been prepared.

By the combination of chromium sulphate and chromic acid or alkali chromates in molecular proportions, chromo-sulpho-chromic acid and the corresponding alkaline salts have also been prepared [Recoura, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1897, iii, 17, 934]. Like the constitution of the chromo-sulphates the constitutions of these compounds may be

These compounds are unstable. A fresh solution is incapable of yielding precipitates with the Ba or Ag salts but does so after 42 hours.

Sarkar and Bhattacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 7, 765) have studied the formation of chromo-seleno-sulphuric acids and their potassium salts. These complexes are prepared by the action of green chromium selenate and selenic acid or sulphuric acid or alkali sulphates in molecular

proportions. Freshly prepared solutions do not give the tests of chromium, sulphate or selenate ions, hence they have the formulae

In the present paper the formation of chromi-selenic acid, chromi-seleni-chromic acids and chromium chromi-seleni-chromate has been studied. These components are generally hygroscopic and soluble in water. The solutions are acidic and freshly prepared solutions do not give any indication of chromic, selenate or chromate ions, except the last compound which gives only the usual test of chromium. So they are all in a complex molecule. These complexes are unstable, the aqueous solutions even at the ordinary temperature decompose after a short time and immediately on heating.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Chromi-selenic Acid.

Green $Cr_2(SeO_4)_3, 13H_2O$, prepared according to the process described in a previous paper (Raychoudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 623) was dissolved in water with difficulty and mixed with selenic acid in molecular proportions. The mixture was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. A green hygroscopic crystalline substance was obtained. It was dried at 120° . The freshly prepared solution did not give any precipitate with ammonium hydroxide or barium nitrate but on boiling precipitates were obtained. {Found : Cr, 15.2 ; Se, 46.1. $H[Cr(SeO_4)_2]$ requires Cr, 15.3 ; Se, 46.6 per cent}.

Tri-selenato-chromic Acid or Acid Chromi-selenate $H_2[Cr(SeO_4)_3]$.

Meyer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 18, 1) obtained the above compound by boiling for a long time the aqueous solution of violet chromium selenate, $[Cr(H_2O)_6]_2(SeO_4)_3, 3H_2O$ and precipitating it as a dark green oil by the addition of a large quantity of alcohol. The green oil when evaporated on the water-bath gave a green compound to which he gave the formula $H_2Cr(SeO_4)_3$.

By boiling solutions of blue $Cr_2(SeO_4)_3, 17H_2O$ and adding alcohol no precipitate was obtained.

On adding a solution of blue $Cr_2(SeO_4)_3, 17H_2O$ (Raychoudhury, *loc. cit.*) to a solution of selenic acid in the proportion of one molecule of the former to three molecules of the latter and evaporating the mixture to dryness on the water-bath, a green crystalline mass was obtained. The green solid was

rubbed with glacial acetic acid, filtered and dried over caustic potash in a vacuum desiccator. {Found : Cr, 10'43 ; Se, 48'51. $H_2[Cr(SeO_4)_2]$ requires Cr, 10'74 ; Se, 48'9 per cent}.

The green compound dissolved easily in cold water giving a greenish acidic solution. Freshly prepared cold solution did not give any precipitate with ammonium hydrate or with barium salts. On boiling and adding barium nitrate or ammonium hydroxide, precipitates were obtained. So chromium and selenium must be within the complex molecule. The reaction may be represented thus

Chromi-seleni-chromic Acids.

Sarkar and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*) prepared chromi-seleni-mono-, di- and tri-sulphuric acids by mixing one, two or three molecular proportions of sulphuric acid with one molecule of green chromi-selenate. Similarly, one molecule of blue $Cr_2(SeO_4)_3, 17H_2O$ was mixed with one, two or three molecules of chromic acid and evaporated in a vacuum desiccator.

(a) *Chromi-seleni-mono-chromic acid* is a brown hygroscopic powder, soluble in water. The yellow solution is acidic. Freshly prepared solutions do not give any precipitate with dilute solutions of silver nitrate, barium nitrate or ammonia. On boiling the complex decomposes. {Found : Cr, 23'85 ; Se, 36'37. $H_2 \left[Cr_2 \begin{matrix} (SeO_4)_3 \\ (CrO_4)_2 \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 23'96 ; Se, 36'41 per cent}.

(b) *Chromi-seleni-di-chromic acid* is a reddish brown powder, very hygroscopic and soluble in water. Freshly prepared solution, which is acidic, does not give any test with the above reagents in the cold, but on boiling the tests are obtained. {Found : Cr, 27'12 ; Se, 31'03. $H_4 \left[Cr_2 \begin{matrix} (SeO_4)_3 \\ (CrO_4)_2 \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 27'05 ; Se, 30'89 per cent}.

(c) *Chromi-seleni-tri-chromic acid* is a chocolate coloured, very hygroscopic powder. It easily dissolves in water making a yellow, acidic solution. Freshly prepared solution does not give any test for chromic, selenate or chromate ions, but on keeping for a short time or on boiling, dilute solutions of silver nitrate, barium nitrate and ammonia give precipitates. {Found : Cr, 30'09 ; Se, 26'93. $H_6 \left[Cr_3 \begin{matrix} (SeO_4)_3 \\ (CrO_4)_3 \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 29'31 ; Se, 26'61 per cent}.

According to Recoura, (*loc. cit.*) the complexes may have the formulae,

or as suggested by Sarkar and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*)

When more than three molecules of chromic acid were mixed with one molecule of blue $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3$, $17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and evaporated on the water bath, a deep chocolate coloured mass was obtained. The mass dissolves readily in water giving a brownish yellow acidic solution which gave a chocolate precipitate of Ag_2CrO_4 with silver nitrate. This proved that the limit of combination had been passed.

Potassium Chromi-seleni-chromates.

By dissolving molecular proportions of the blue $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3$, $17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and potassium chromate in the ratios 1 to 1, 2 or 3 molecules simultaneously in water and evaporating on the water-bath, yellow or brown powders were obtained. They are soluble in water giving yellow solutions which give no precipitate with ammonia, barium nitrate and silver nitrate. On heating, the tests of Cr, SeO_4 and CrO_4 are obtained.

They are the corresponding salts of the above acids, thus

(a) Found : Cr, 21.6 ; Se, 32.7. $\text{K}_2 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \\ (\text{CrO}_4) \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 21.47 ; Se, 32.59 per cent.

(b) Found : Cr, 22.7 ; Se, 25.8. $\text{K}_4 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \\ (\text{CrO}_4)_2 \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 22.58 ; Se, 25.73 per cent.

(c) Found : Cr, 23.9 ; Se, 21.20. $\text{K}_6 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \\ (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \end{matrix} \right]$ requires Cr, 23.86 ; Se, 21.26 per cent.

Chromium Chromi-selenato-sulphate.

An aqueous solution of one molecule of green chromium sulphate was evaporated with an aqueous solution of three molecules of green chromium

selenate on a water-bath. A green powder, difficultly soluble in water, was obtained. Excess of ammonium hydroxide gave a precipitate of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ in the ice-cold solution; on filtering and boiling the filtrate with excess of ammonia again $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ was precipitated. So chromium is also in the complex. Dilute solution of barium nitrate gives no precipitate in the freshly prepared cold solution but on boiling a precipitate is obtained, showing that SeO_4 and SO_4 are in the complex. {Found: Cr, 21.10; Se, 36.02; SO_4 , 14.7. $\text{Cr}_2 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SeO}_4)_2 \\ (\text{SO}_4) \end{matrix} \right]_2$ requires Cr, 20.89; Se, 35.71; SO_4 , 14.41 per cent}.

Chromium Chromi-sulphato-selenate.

By mixing three molecules of chromium sulphate with one molecule of green chromium selenate and evaporating in the water-bath, a green powder was formed. Excess of ammonia gave a precipitate of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ in the freshly prepared ice-cold solution. On filtering and boiling, again $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ is precipitated proving that chromium is also in the complex. Dilute solutions of barium nitrate gives no precipitate with freshly prepared cold solution, but on boiling a white precipitate is obtained, showing that SeO_4 and SO_4 are in the complex. {Found Cr, 24.52; Se, 13.50; SO_4 , 51.23. $\text{Cr}_2 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SO}_4)_2 \\ (\text{SeO}_4) \end{matrix} \right]_2$ requires Cr, 24.34; Se, 13.87; SO_4 , 50.56 per cent}.

Chromium Chromi-selenato-chromate.

By dissolving equimolecular proportions of chromium chromi-chromate $\text{Cr} \left[\text{Cr} \begin{matrix} (\text{CrO}_4)_2 \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \end{matrix} \right]$ and green chromium selenate $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ simultaneously in water and evaporating in the water-bath, a dark red or chocolate powder was obtained. It is difficultly soluble in water. The freshly prepared cooled solution, when treated with excess of NH_4OH gave a precipitate. After filtration, the filtrate when boiled with excess of ammonia again gives a precipitate of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$. The freshly prepared solution gives no test for CrO_4 and SeO_4 ions in the cold, but after a very short time (less than half an hour) or immediately if heated, the complex decomposes. {Found Cr^{III} , 20.93; Cr^{VI} , 16.20; Se, 24.3. $\text{Cr}_2 \left[\text{Cr}_2 \begin{matrix} (\text{SeO}_4)_2 \\ (\text{CrO}_4)_2 \end{matrix} \right]_2$ requires Cr^{III} , 21.11; Cr^{VI} , 15.83; Se, 24.06 per cent}.

Chromium Chromi-dichromate.

Calcagni (*Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 396) by evaporating a solution of Cr_2O_3 in H_2CrO_4 obtained a hygroscopic, amorphous paste, which he named chromium dichromate.

By adopting the above process, no such compound was obtained.

When an aqueous solution of one molecule of chromium chromi-chromate, $\text{Cr} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \\ \text{Cr} \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \end{array} \right]$ was mixed with an aqueous solution containing three molecules of chromic acid and carefully evaporated in the water-bath, deep chocolate coloured shining crystals were obtained. The following table gives a comparative study of the properties of the above compound, chromic acid and chromium chromi-chromate.

TABLE I.

Reagent.	H_2CrO_4 .	New compound.	$\text{Cr} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \\ \text{Cr} \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \end{array} \right]$.
Water.	Readily soluble.	Difficultly soluble (acidic solution).	Difficultly soluble (acidic solution).
$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.	Yellow ppt.	Brown ppt. after sometime.	Brown ppt. after sometime
$\text{Pb}(\text{Ac})_2$.	Immediate yellow ppt.	Do	Do
NH_4OH	—	Bluish brown ppt.	Bluish brown ppt.
AgNO_3 (conc. soln.)	Black ppt.	Voluminous red ppt.	Small quantity of red ppt.
AgNO_3 (very dil. soln.)	Reddish ppt.	No. ppt.	No. ppt.

Since the above compound resembles $\text{Cr} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \\ \text{Cr} \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \end{array} \right]$ more than H_2CrO_4

so the reaction may be regarded as follows :

Found : Cr_2O_3 , 18.5 ; CrO_3 , 75.1 ; Cr_2O_3 , 6 CrO_3 , 3 H_2O requires Cr_2O_3 , 18.86 ; CrO_3 , 74.44 per cent.

My sincere thanks are due to Dr. P. B. Sarkar for suggesting this piece of work.